

Status and experience of women worker in job market of Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

About half of the total population of Bangladesh is women. Most of them are working at various job fields now and facing lot of problem in forwarding. Now a days women are engaging many kinds of job and often which is the only source of income of her family. This study examines the effect of different problems faced by the working women in their job field. Most of them are not fully satisfied with their salary some are facing physical assault or harassment at their work place or at road. Most of them are not getting proper transportation facilities. Most of the problems faced by the women arises at ready-made garments sectors. The women who are working at the industry, bank, hospital, office, engineering farm, school, college also faced similar or less similar kind of problems. They are discriminated by the male less or more at the entire working sector. From the bivariate analysis it was observed that Job place, Salary, Much time stay in job, Night duty, Educational qualification have significant relation with the job doing by the female workers. To overcome the barriers respective authorities should take appreciate measures considering the factors observed by this study and others which must be needed for the improvement of women's employment.

Introduction

Since long run the women of Bangladeshi women have been struggling to establish their rights in family, society and in the state. The history of Bangladesh speaks that in any type of revolution or in constructive change, both men and women worked hand by hand. They put equal contribution of the women directly or indirectly is unmemorable.

Family is natural and historical shelter for the people. We know that all types of education originate from the family. When a child born then he or she started gradually to understand everything by following their parents. The reflection of the behavioral attitude between the parents integrated in the children. That is why parents should take care of rearing and bearing of the children and should be conscious in giving them education and imparted values to them. In any cases there should not be developed within them the idea that the girl is subordinate to the boys. No parents should give privilege to the son only.

Our society is mainly patriarchal in nature, so that either father or any other male person dominated the family. As a result discrimination develops between the boys and girls, boys are considered to be an asset and the girls are considered as liabilities of the family. It is very stereotyping thinking of the society that only the mother and daughter should work household besides father and son will earn and govern the family. So discrimination starts

from the family. Family is the strongest driving force for molding the children into the right direction. If the family's impact is negative on this regard, then we could not expect any justice to society. In the rural area of Bangladesh, the thinking is like this that the son will conceive the name of father and girl will not because she will go to her husband's home.

Dowry related violence is a common feature in Bangladesh affecting the lives of many women. Other than specific acts of violence, such as killing, torture, throwing of acid and the like, dowry demands affect the lives of women socially and culturally in a much deeper manner. Fundamentally, they undermine the equality of women and create culturally accepted forms of discrimination against them. They can affect the life of a girl from the very start. Preference for boys often begins with the parental realization that the burden of finding dowries falls on them as soon as the child is born. Thus the devaluation of a child takes place in culturally subtle forms from the very beginning. This continues throughout their early years and up to the time of marriage.

The present study was undertaken to find out the discrimination over the alleviating working women in Bangladesh in order to find out i) which kind of working women are getting more victimized of discrimination. ii. To get the actual scenario of the working women in their job station. iii. to find out what kind of problems actually they are facing. iv. To get the real situation of the working women in

her own family. iv. to evaluate the actual job facilities of employed women in Bangladesh.

Methodology

A purposive sample of 100 earning women in Chattagram division in Bangladesh was taken for collecting information. A structured questionnaire was prepared which were subjected to pre-test to make it complete, precise and meaningful. Only one earning woman in each family was subjected to interview although there were sometimes two earning women in some joint family household.

We adopted a system of house to house, factory to factory and different places, based on 50 questions for female respondents. Method for data collection was to read out the question and where not understandable explain by citing examples of realistic situation in the domestic setting. Replies were recorded at the time of interview. The author had to stay in the selected areas for couple of days for gaining deeper insight into the social and rural system beyond the information obtained from their direct replies to questions.

The questionnaire was prepared carefully, keeping in mind the main aspects that include question sequence, formulation and wording. First of all a draft questionnaire was prepared then it was discussed with the supervisor. After a thorough discussion, all questions were re-examined and revised and then a pre-test was conducted on 20 respondents in the survey area. After the pre-test some questions were modified according to the information from the pre-test and some unnecessary questions were dropped, and the questionnaire was finalized.

Variables

The variables in this study were chosen on the basis of prior knowledge and initial explainer data analysis. These variable are stated in the results section.

Bivariate analysis

To study whether there is an association of using dependent variable and independent variables of the women (X_2) test statistics is performed after constructing the contingency table. The test statistics is_

$X_2 = \sum \sum (O_{ij} - E_{ij}) / E_{ij}$ with (r-1) (c-1) degrees of freedom,

Where, the null and alternative hypothesis is as follows;

H_0 : There is no association between dependent and independent variables.

H_1 : There is association between dependent and independent variables.

Statistical analysis

For performing this analysis a technological support is necessary. In this study, the entire analysis is done in SPSS (Statistical package for social science) windows version 20. The program produces lists, frequencies, cross tabulation and variety of other results. Besides SPSS other well-known package like MS word, MS excel were also used.

Table 2: Background characteristics of respondents

Educational qualification	Frequency	Percent
Graduate	19	19.0
Higher secondary	18	18.0
Illiterate	9	9.0
primary	32	32.0
Secondary	22	22.0
Total	100	100.0
Marital status		
Married	34	34.0
Others	26	26.0
Single	40	40.0
Total	100	100.0
Staying		
Alone	15	15.0
Husbands house	29	29.0
Parents house	56	56.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2: Nature and experience of job of the respondents

Job category	Frequency	Percent
Garments worker	42	42.0
Office staffs	20	20.0
Others	38	38.0
Total	100	100.0
Job place		
Near home	58	58.0
Remote areas	42	42.0
Total	100	100.0
Salary		
Monthly 11001-above	10	10.0
Monthly 3000-7000	52	52.0

Monthly 7001-11000	38	38.0
Total	100	100.0
Job duration		
1-5 year	42	42.0
5-10 years	16	16.0
Less than 1 ye	31	31.0
Others	11	11.0
Total	100	100.0
Much time stay job		
1-8 hours	73	73.0
Others	27	27.0
Total	100	100.0
Night duty		
No	25	25.0
Sometimes	36	36.0
Yes	39	39.0
Total	100	100.0
Any experience		
No	34	34.0
Yes	66	66.0
Total	100	100.0
Left previous job		
Bad behavior of	15	15.0
Child birth	3	3.0
Employers	34	34.0
Factory lay off	2	2.0
Got better job	3	3.0
Got no promotion	4	4.0
Insecure commuting	7	7.0
Irregular wage pa	11	11.0
Long working hour	2	2.0
Low pay	9	9.0
Marriage	3	3.0
Mother in law	6	6.0
unwillingness	1	1.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 3: Facilities for the women associated with their job

Family support	Frequency	Percent
No	62	62.0
Yes	38	38.0
Total	100	100.0
Rest room facilities		
No	100	100.0
Proper toilet facilities		
No	72	72.0
Yes	28	28.0
Total	100	100.0
Transport facilities		
No	80	80.0
Yes	20	20.0
Total	100	100.0

Proper health support		
Get little support	18	18.0
Neglected	82	82.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4: Problems associated with the women workers

Face any problem	Frequency	Percent
Family	21	21.0
Non-cooperation	28	28.0
Transportation	51	51.0
Total	100	100.0
Problem in your educational institution		
No	29	29.0
No comment	8	8.0
Yes	63	63.0
Total	100	100.0
Causal leave opportunity		
No	60	60.0
On request	18	18.0
Yes	22	22.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4: Discrimination attitude towards women worker

Salary status	Frequency	Percent
Equal	22	22.0
Unequal	78	78.0
Total	100	100.0
Awkward behave		
Grabbing	14	14.0
Insult directed at gender	34	34.0
Others	13	13.0
Remarks to unwelcome touching suggestive comments	20	20.0
Total	19	19.0
Total	100	100.0
Captain of the class		
A boy	63	63.0
A girl	29	29.0
No comment	8	8.0
Total	100	100.0
Same respect as compare to male		
No	86	86.0
Social prejudice against women	14	14.0
Total	100	100.0
Cause of the female don't get seat at public transportation		
Male does not leave the seat by seeing a standing women	74	74.0
They does not take the seat	26	26.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 5: Vulnerability of women worker in the job and society

Victimized of physical assault and sexual harassment	Frequency	Percent
Anywhere	57	57.0
At home	5	5.0
At road	20	20.0
At work place	18	18.0
Total	100	100.0
Early married, could not build up their career		
Others	3	3.0
Their parents force them to get married because of poverty	93	93.0
They used as a earning member by their family	4	4.0
Total	100	100.0
Dowry affecting		
Dowry is taken by male from female	38	38.0
For this female are tortured by male which is inhumanities	62	62.0
Total	100	100.0
Divorce		
Divorce are fully controlled by the in our society	69	69.0
It's an autocratic system	31	31.0
Total	100	100.0
Done home work alone after returning from job		
No	66	66.0
Yes	34	34.0
Total	100	100.0
Attend any kind of social function		
No	61	61.0
Sometimes	18	18.0
Yes	21	21.0
Total	100	100.0
Eve teasing		
No	21	21.0
Yes	79	79.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 6: Cause of discrimination against women

Cause of men employee is more than the women	Frequency	Percent
Job requiring operation of heavy machinery	17	17.0
Lack of professional training	9	9.0
They don't get enough facilities	33	33.0
Women's preference to work at a secure place near home	41	41.0
Total	100	100.0
Cause of Decision making should be taken by male person	Frequency	Percent

Because of social rule female are incapable of taking power	40	40.0
Male think female are poor decision maker	60	60.0
Total	100	100.0

Rural area did not get higher education

Financial problem	3	3.0
Limited mobility	9	9.0
Not enough facilities, financial problem	33	33.0
Not enough facilities, financial problem, early marriage	40	40.0
Parents awareness	15	15.0
Total	100	100.0

Dependency

Her father	45	45.0
Her husband	21	21.0
Self-dependent	34	34.0
Total	100	100.0

Asset

Not a single	46	46.0
One third of whole asset	54	54.0
Total	100	100.0

Bivariate analysis

Relationship between the respondent's job category and characteristics were assessed by bivariate analysis. This analysis imposes the impact on the relation or association of women characteristic with the job categories in order to take measure to solve the problem in job place.

Table 7: Bivariate relationships between respondent's characteristics and job categories

Characteristics	Pearson Chi-Square value	p value (Asymp. Sig. (2-sided))
Marital status	4.199	0.380
Job category (Office stuffs, Garments workers and others)	1.221	0.875
Staying with	12.252	0.002*
Job place	2.389 ^a	0.665
Job duration	24.067 ^a	0.000*
Salary	40.655 ^a	0.000*
Much time stay in job	44.043 ^a	0.000*
Night duty	15.831 ^a	0.003*
Record	0.755 ^a	0.686
Educational qualification	9.813 ^a	0.007*
Record		
Any experience		
Family		

support		
Proper toilet facilities	0.833	0.659
Transport facilities	100.000	0.000*
Causal leave opportunity	42.323 ^a	0.000*
Salary status	29.107 ^a	0.000*
Face any problem	28.450 ^a	0.000*
Awkward behave	48.881 ^a	0.000*
Problem in educational institution	21.722 ^a	0.000*
Captain in the class	21.722 ^a	0.000*
Some respect as compare to male	0.774 ^a	0.679
Cause of female worker violated by male worker	1.443 ^a	0.002*
Cause of female worker violated by male worker	1.443 ^a	0.837
Victimized of physically assault and sexual	9.810 ^a	0.044*
Early marriage could not build up their career	8.400 ^a	0.015*
cause of more men worker than woman	9.550 ^a	0.049*
Rural woman area did not get higher education	4.789 ^a	0.091
Cause of decision making should be taken by male person	1.811 ^a	0.404
Dowry affecting	23.155 ^a	0.061
Divorce	5.581 ^a	0.061
Dependency	9.831 ^a	0.043*
Eve teasing	.274 ^a	0.872
Asset	4.964 ^a	0.084
Done home work alone after returning from job	3.377 ^a	0.185

Attend any kind of social function	6.826 ^a	0.033
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From the bivariate analysis it was observed that job place, salary, much time stay in job, night duty, educational qualification, casual leave, salary status, facing problems, awkward behave, problem in institution, captain of the class, violated by male, early marriage higher education facility have significant relation with the job doing by the female workers.

Similarly family support, transport facilities, salary status, victimized of physically assault and sexual, Attending any kind of social function have significant impact on job of women. Surprisingly, some of the characteristic do not have significant relationship with job categories of women worker. For example marital status, place of residence, job duration, rest room and toilet facilities facilities. Even experiences, divorce, eve teasing donot have significant relation in job place (Table 7).

In a standard labour supply function, education is often included as a key determinant of labour supply, and most of the literature finds a significant positive impact of education on the labour supply decision of women (Rahman and Islam, 2013; Mahmud and Bidisha, 2018; Raihan and Jahan, 2018).

Results and Discussion

The most discriminated women are garments worker with a view to the point of educational qualification and their percentage is 26%. On the basis of salary garments worker are the lowest paid and they stay more at their first job. The duration of staying at first job (1-5 years) is 18%. The percentage of low paid garments worker is 22%. There are many types of alleviating working women but the most have to do night duty is garments worker and their percentage is 41%. The women working at garments sector get less family support than the others and their percentage is 32%. Women works now a days outside home but they don't get proper facilities as compare to male. Such as 42% even not get restroom facilities, 29% don't get proper toilet facilities and 42% women don't get daycare facilities at their job place. Transportation facilities in any kind of office are very poor in Bangladesh. But it is worst for the lady staff and 42% ladies staff not gets the facilities of transportation. Women discriminated

by male because of awkward behavior at the office is 42%. 33% women don't get their actual casual leave. 32.6% women discriminated at their educational institutions. 37% women who work at outside not get proper respect from male colleague. Women in Bangladesh getting proper health care are very little and most of them are neglected from health support and which is 36%.

The most (20%) of women worker get violated at their work place. 22% of them are victimized of physical assault and sexual harassment by male at job station. 24% rural women don't get proper facilities for their higher education and 42% women could not build their career because of early marriage. 37% working women thinks that dowry affecting physical tortured for women which is committed by male. Now a days woman are working outside and faced eve teasing almost every day from elder and younger at road and which become social problem. The percentage of women faced eve teasing is 34%. 30% women didn't get the chance of attending social function by their own and which is a great discrimination to the female.

In many cases, women are not safe at the workplace, especially in the manufacturing sector in Bangladesh since they have been harassed either by their male colleagues or supervisors (Ali & Islam, 2017; Sarker, 2014; Sarker & Akter, 2018).

Women workers in Bangladesh are betrayed, abused, and harassed by their male counter parts in different ways (Haque et al., 2019). Several studies have identified that women who have experienced sexual harassment in the workplace do not want to continue their jobs with male colleagues (Ali, et al., 2018). In this study Victimized of physically assault and sexual as significant relation with job category.

Conclusion

Gender discrimination is a curse to any society and if we don't remove it from the roots it will rotten the society. If we look in the details of the research work we can see that working women faced great problems created by male. They are often humiliated by the men at any place. They are not properly safe at road, at office, at work place even at home. If we want their best from their profession we have honor them and help them. Every man has to concern about their respect and honor. About 42% women economically helped their family and

by doing this they strengthen our national economy. If our men changed their attitude, as a result more woman could get involved in different profession. We have to inspire them not to do something which dissatisfies them.

Suggestion

Now a day's woman proved their importance to their family, to the society and for the country. It is duty to give them a fresh and a safe environment and also give them their dignity. Every authority has to provide gender friendly environment which would have to free from any kind of harassment. Besides this government should have to impose law against gender discrimination at job place and also ensure proper application of it. Government also has to take steps for concerning about it among the people.

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